

Adsorption characteristics of a metal-organic framework material for the removal of Acid Orange 10 from aqueous solutions[†]

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Abstract : The study of adsorption characteristics of a metal organic framework material (Cu-DTO) for the adsorptive removal of a hazardous dye, Acid Orange 10 (AO-10) from aqueous solutions was undertaken. Cu-DTO complex showed fast adsorption with an equilibrium time of 20 min. Lower concentration range favored the removal. Solution pH also influenced the adsorption process and removal was higher at lower pH. The adsorption isotherm study revealed that Freundlich model fitted the data better indicating a multilayer adsorption on the surface of adsorbent. The adsorption capacity decreased with increasing temperature and maximum adsorption capacity of the Cu-DTO was found to be 3.14×10^{-4} mol/g at 303 K. Kinetic study indicated that process of removal followed pseudo-second order kinetics. The removal of the dye was spontaneous. Desorption studies revealed that the adsorbent could be used without loss of capacity for two cycles.

Keywords : Cu-DTO complex, Acid Orange 10 (AO-10), adsorption, isotherm.

Introduction

Rapid industrialization and modernization of agriculture creates an intense impact on our existing water resources. Day by day, vulnerability of the hydric resources for contamination with industrial and agricultural based pollutants is increasing sternly, which on the other hand disrupts the self regenerating capacities of natural water bodies. It is therefore, prime requirement that the industrial discharges must be treated prior to their disposal into the receiving streams. Major contaminants which severely deteriorate the quality of water and harm flora and fauna include heavy metals, fertilizers, pesticides, pharmaceutical products, radioactive wastes, and wastes from paper and pulp industries, textile industries, and oil refineries. Color is an effluent characteristic, which is easily detected and readily traced back to its source¹. Color is the most obvious indicator of the water pollution². Moreover, presence of dyes and pigments can be easily discernable even at minute levels (1.0 mg/L)³. These

colored materials possess complex chemical structure that makes them very stable to light, several chemicals, oxidizing agents and heat. Removal of these compounds at low levels is indeed a cumbersome task. Several treatment technologies based on the conventional know-how such as coagulation, flocculation, ozonation, reverse osmosis, biological oxidation, chemical precipitation etc. were devoted purposefully for the decolorization of wastewater and the pros and cons of these techniques have been reviewed at length⁴ but as such, none of these methods is perfect, besides suffered from various setback, for instance these methods are selective, expensive, require special infrastructure and maintenance. The use of adsorption technology has gained worldwide attention as it is considered to be the most effective and proven technology having wide prospective applications in both water and wastewater treatment.

Range of adsorbents has been tested for its potential in adsorptive removal of the dyes from the aqueous solu-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

tions among which activated carbon has been considered as the most appealing due its high degree of effectiveness. However, high running costs of activated carbons let the scientific community to explore certain alternatives and equally effective materials in terms of high surface area and porosity. Such adsorbents were activated carbon derived from agricultural based materials⁵⁻⁸, zeolites⁹, layered double hydroxides¹⁰, magnetic Fe₃O₄-activated carbon nanocomposite¹¹, and magnetic alginate beads¹². Recently a new class of materials, better known as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), that exhibiting compatible characteristics of activated carbons have been investigated for the removal of hazardous materials. MOFs are the new families of porous crystalline materials that have many potential advantages over the traditional adsorbents¹³. MOFs are composed of two major components : a metal ion or a cluster of metal ions and an organic molecule called a linker. The organic units are typically di-, tri-, or tetradentate ligands¹⁴. Increasing interest in MOF type material is due to its exceptionally high porosity, easy tunability of their pore size and shape from microporous to mesoporous scale by changing the connectivity of the inorganic moiety and the nature of the organic linkers¹⁵. MOFs are thus regarded as promising materials for adsorption-related applications. The easy modification of their pore surfaces which leads to the selective adsorption of some specific guest molecules having particular functional groups¹⁴ makes them more useful for adsorption applications. These fascinating attributes of MOFs facilitate its use and application in the field of gas storage¹⁵, drug delivery¹⁶, luminescence¹⁷, separation of chemicals¹⁸, catalysts¹⁹. The present study is addressed to the application of one of the metal-organic framework materials formed by the complexation of copper with the ligand dithiooxamide (Cu-DTO complex), for the adsorptive removal of Acid Orange 10. A few MOFs such as chromium-benzenedicarboxylate complex and iron-benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylate (BTC) have been reported for the removal of methyl orange²⁰ and malachite green²¹ respectively from the aqueous solutions. However, so far, Cu-DTO complex has been used as an adsorbent for the removal of crystal violet²² from aqueous solutions. Effects of various operating parameters, adsorption isotherm, thermodynamics and kinetics of AO-10 have been reported in this article. Structure of the dye has been provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of Acid Orange 10.

Results and discussion

The FTIR spectrum of the adsorbent is displayed in Fig. 2. In order to confirm whether Cu-DTO complex formation has taken place the FTIR of both the 'pure DTO' along with 'Cu-DTO complex' were conducted. The peaks at 3482, 3376 and 3302 cm⁻¹ were there due to stretching of amine group of DTO, whereas for Cu-DTO complex, the peaks shifted to slightly lower frequencies at 3426 and 3244 cm⁻¹ indicating the formation of metal-nitrogen bond²³ and may be due to O-H stretching vibration²².

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of DTO and Cu-DTO complex.

The peak at 1598 cm⁻¹ in DTO ascribed to C-N stretching vibration, whereas for Cu-DTO complex, the peak shifted to 1506 cm⁻¹ and the peaks were observed in both the case within the range of 1300–1450 cm⁻¹ contribute

to $\delta(\text{NH})$ vibration²⁴. The C=S stretching vibration of the complex is represented by the adsorption band at 1199 cm^{-1} and it was splitted into two peaks at 1139 and 1064 cm^{-1} because of the formation of metal-sulphur bond.

The XRD pattern of the prepared material Cu-DTO complex has been given in Fig. 3. The three characteristic peaks ($2\theta \approx 8.5^\circ$, 17.2° and 28.1°), corresponding to distance between adjacent atoms of (10.47, 5.21, 3.26 nm) were present in the samples. The similar peaks were observed by Li *et al.*²² also for the Cu-DTO complex.

Fig. 3 XRD record of Cu-DTO complex.

The crystal structure of the Cu-DTO was found to be a framework like constitution having two dimensional arrangements composed of Cu-dimeric units bridging with the ligands as represented in Fig. 4. The results of FTIR and XRD indicated that the Cu-DTO complex was synthesized successfully under the experimental conditions.

Effect of initial pH :

The pH of the solution plays an important role in adsorption process, particularly affecting the adsorption capacity²⁵. In the present study, the effect of pH on adsorption process was studied over a pH range of 2–10 at 303 K. Up to this range of pH, there was insignificant change in the absorbance of the dye solution; however at a pH > 10, there is marked decrease in absorbance which affects the spectrophotometric determination of residual concentration of the dye. The effect of pH on the adsorption of AO-10 by Cu-DTO complex has been depicted in Fig. 5. It was observed that adsorption capacity of the MOFs decreased rapidly with increase of pH. The maximum removal (99%) with adsorption capacity of $8.7 \times 10^{-6}\text{ mol/g}$ was achieved at pH 2 and afterward the removal of the dye decreased rapidly to 42.3%, with dye uptake capacity of $2.4 \times 10^{-6}\text{ mol/g}$ at pH 7. The adsorption of dyes after pH 7 and up to 10 was almost constant. The change in adsorption capacity of the adsorbent with the change of pH may be attributed to the surface active sites that are possessed by the adsorbent material and are responsible for uptake of dye. The number of these sites gets affected with the change of chemistry of the solute in the solution. When the solution is acidic, the adsorbent surface becomes prominently protonated and acquires positive charge which enhances removal of anionic dye ions through electrostatic forces of attraction²⁶. Further, the sulfate group existing on AO-10 molecules will undergo

Fig. 4. Cu-DTO complex having framework like structure with 2D arrangement.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on removal of AO-10 (dye concentration $2.2 \times 10^{-5} M$; temperature 303 K; adsorbent dose 1 g/L).

a strong electrostatic interaction with an adsorbent having a positive charge.

Effect of initial dye concentration :

The effect of initial concentration of the dye on removal of the dye, AO-10 has been given in Fig. 6. The study was conducted at the initial concentrations of 2.21×10^{-5} , 5.52×10^{-5} , 1.11×10^{-4} and $1.66 \times 10^{-4} M$ and it was found that the removal was highly concentration-dependent. All adsorption experiments reached equilibrium within 20 min of the batch experiments. It can be seen from Fig. 6 that the maximum removal (%) of dye ions is for lowest concentration of the dye solution. The 'initial concentration versus adsorption capacity profile'

Fig. 6. Effect of initial concentration on removal of AO-10 (pH 2; temperature 303 K; adsorbent dose 1 g/L).

depicts inverse correlation to that of initial concentration versus % removal. As from the plot it is clear that with the increase of dye concentration, the capacity of adsorbent increases simultaneously and at higher concentration of $1.66 \times 10^{-4} M$ of dye ions, the adsorption capacity was found to be $1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/g}$ while at lower dye concentration of $2.21 \times 10^{-5} M$, the adsorption capacity was reduced to $8.72 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol/g}$. This can be explained on the basis of driving force that is offered by the large amount of dye ions present in more concentrated solutions which consequently leads to mass transfer of ions over solid phase from liquid phase²⁶.

Adsorption isotherm :

The adsorption isotherm data were fitted with Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. Both models help in explaining the interaction of the adsorbate with adsorbent. The Langmuir isotherm model assumes monolayer coverage of the surface adsorption in which adsorption takes place only at specific homogeneous sites that are present over the adsorbent surface. Unlike the Langmuir's model, Freundlich isotherm model suggest that adsorption occurs with multi-layer coverage of adsorbate over adsorbent with heterogeneous sites.

Langmuir isotherm can be represented in linearized form²⁷ :

$$C_e/q_e = 1/Q_{\max} b + C_e/Q_{\max} \tag{1}$$

where C_e (M), q_e (mol/g) are the concentrations of adsor-

bate and amount of adsorbate adsorbed at equilibrium, respectively. The constant b (L/mol) is the Langmuir equilibrium constant and Q_{\max} gives the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity. The linear plots of C_e/q_e versus C_e were plotted at three different temperatures and the values of various parameters are given in Table 1. The maximum monolayer adsorption capacities of the adsorbent decreased with increasing temperature indicates that dye adsorption is exothermic in nature.

Table 1. Various parameters of adsorption isotherm for removal of AO-10

Langmuir isotherm :

Temperature (K)	Q_{\max} (mol/g)	b (L/mol)	R^2
303	3.14×10^{-4}	9.5×10^{-5}	0.947
313	2.89×10^{-4}	5.7×10^{-5}	0.976
323	2.82×10^{-4}	4.6×10^{-5}	0.981

Freundlich isotherm :

Temperature (K)	K_F (mol/g)	n	R^2
303	1.6×10^{-5}	3.12	0.978
313	8.5×10^{-6}	1.89	0.999
323	8.1×10^{-6}	1.99	0.999

The Freundlich isotherm model²⁸ is expressed as :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \quad (2)$$

K_f (mol/g) is the Freundlich constant and n is the Freundlich exponent. The equilibrium data was plotted for ‘log q_e versus log C_e ’ enables the constant K_f and exponent $1/n$ to be determined. q_e is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbate, C_e the equilibrium concentration, and $1/n$ and K_f are constants. The constant K_f is related to the degree of adsorption, $1/n$ provides the tentative estimation of the intensity of the adsorption. The values of Freundlich parameters ‘ K_f ’ and ‘ $1/n$ ’ are given in Table 1. Linear plots (Fig. 7) with good correlation coefficient values confirm that Freundlich isotherm better fitted the isotherm data as compared with Langmuir isotherm model. This further suggests that the adsorption of AO-10 over Cu-DTO complex takes place in multi-layer manner.

Adsorption kinetics :

The adsorption kinetics of AO-10 onto Cu-DTO was investigated in order to determine rate controlling steps by means of two kinetic models, namely the Lagergren pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model. The

Fig. 7. Freundlich isotherm for adsorption of AO-10 onto Cu-DTO complex at three different temperatures.

Lagergren rate equation is one of the most widely used rate equations for the adsorption of solute from a liquid solution²⁹. The pseudo-first order kinetic model³⁰ can be expressed by the following equation :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - (K_{ad}/2.303).t \quad (3)$$

The pseudo-second order kinetics³¹ in linearized form can be expressed as :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t \quad (4)$$

where K_{ad} is the pseudo-first order rate constant (min^{-1}) and k_2 , pseudo-second order rate constant (min g/mol) and q_e is the amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium (mol/g), q_t is the amount of dye adsorbed at time t (mol/g).

Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic parameters of AO-10 adsorption for different initial dye concentrations are summarized in Table 2, and plots of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models are shown in Figs. 8 and 9 respectively. The pseudo-second order gives better correlation coefficient, R^2 0.999, as compared to the pseudo-first order. The values of the q_e estimated using pseudo-second order model were more consistent with the experimental data, suggesting the applicability of this model for the adsorption process further the model conveys that chemisorption might be rate limiting step for the sorption of AO-10 over Cu-DTO complex.

Effect of temperature and contact time :

The dependence of the adsorption capacity of AO-10 on temperature has been investigated by carrying out the

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for the removal of AO-10 by adsorption on Cu-DTO complex for different concentrations

Pseudo-first order :			
Concentration (M)	k_1 (L/min)	R^2	$q_{e, cal}/q_{e, exp}$ (mol/g)
2.2×10^{-5}	0.127	0.987	$3.43 \times 10^{-6}/8.7 \times 10^{-6}$
5.52×10^{-5}	0.062	0.990	$6.12 \times 10^{-6}/1.8 \times 10^{-5}$
1.11×10^{-4}	0.034	0.792	$8.71 \times 10^{-6}/3.4 \times 10^{-5}$
1.66×10^{-4}	0.021	0.644	$1.16 \times 10^{-6}/4.8 \times 10^{-5}$
Pseudo-second order :			
Concentration (M)	k_2 (g/mol/min)	R^2	$q_{e, cal}/q_{e, exp}$ (mol/g)
2.2×10^{-5}	1.43×10^{-5}	0.999	$9.02 \times 10^{-6}/8.7 \times 10^{-6}$
5.52×10^{-5}	1.96×10^{-5}	0.997	$1.94 \times 10^{-5}/1.8 \times 10^{-5}$
1.11×10^{-4}	2.42×10^{-5}	0.997	$3.72 \times 10^{-5}/3.4 \times 10^{-5}$
1.66×10^{-4}	3.11×10^{-5}	0.999	$4.86 \times 10^{-5}/4.8 \times 10^{-5}$

Fig. 8. Kinetics pseudo-first order plot at four different concentrations (pH 2, temperature 303 K; adsorbent dose 1 g/L).

Fig. 9. Kinetics pseudo-second order plot at four different concentrations (pH 2; temperature 303 K; adsorbent dose 1 g/L).

experiments at three different temperatures (303, 313 and 323) K. Fig. 10 show that the removal (%) increased with the decrease of temperature which indicated that the adsorption process was exothermic. This characteristic may be attributed to weakening of the bonds between the

Fig. 10. Effect of temperature and contact time on removal (dye concentration 2.2×10^{-5} M, pH 2; adsorbent dose 1 g/L).

dye molecules and the binding sites of the adsorbent or may be due to the either decrease in active sites over surface of adsorbent. This can also result because of increase in the thickness of the boundary layer surrounding the adsorbent with the increase of temperature²⁶. The adsorption of AO-10 takes place rapidly within first 15 min, and the rapid uptake is due to the availability of large amount of surface for sorption of the dye molecules. At higher contact time, the removal rate declines gradually leading to equilibrium. This decline is due to decrease in total surface area and less available binding sites of the adsorbent for the dye molecules.

Adsorption thermodynamics :

For the better understanding of adsorption mechanism, values of various thermodynamic parameters namely free energy change (ΔG_{ads}), enthalpy change (H_{ads}) and entropy change (ΔS_{ads}) for the removal of AO-10 were determined using following equations³² :

$$\ln b = (\Delta S_{ads}/R) - (\Delta H_{ads}/RT) \tag{5}$$

where R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol K), and T is the absolute temperature (K). The values ΔH_{ads} and ΔS_{ads} were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the plot

In b versus $1/T$ (Graph not shown). The values of ΔG_{ads} can be calculated using following equation :

$$\Delta G_{\text{ads}} = \Delta H_{\text{ads}} - T\Delta S_{\text{ads}} \quad (6)$$

The values of the thermodynamic parameters were present in Table 3. The negative values of ΔG_{ads} for all the three temperatures suggest the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process. The increase of the values of ΔG_{ads} as temperature decreases indicates about the affinity of AO-

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of AO-10 on Cu-DTO complex at different temperatures

Temp. (T) (K)	Standard Gibbs free energy change ΔG_{ads} (kJ/mol)	Standard enthalpy change ΔH_{ads} (kJ/mol)	Standard entropy change ΔS_{ads} (J/mol K)
303	-15.41	-41.47	-86.48
313	-14.58		
323	-13.69		

10 for Cu-DTO complex was higher at lower temperature. The negative value of ΔH_{ads} indicates that adsorption of AO-10 over Cu-DTO complex is exothermic in nature. The negative value of ΔS_{ads} (-86.48 J/mol K) suggested that there was decrease in the degree randomness at the solid/liquid interface occurring in the internal structure during the adsorption process.

Regeneration of the adsorbent :

10 mg of adsorbent samples loaded with AO-10 was suspended in 10 mL of Na_2CO_3 (0.5 mol L^{-1}) solution and stirred for 4 h at room temperature. The rehydration products were separated by centrifugation, washed several times with ethanol followed by distilled water, and was dried at 70°C over night. The resultant material was then examined and its adsorption capacity was compared with that of original adsorbent material. The effect of four consecutive adsorption-desorption cycles was studied and the results are illustrated in Fig. 11. From this figure, it can be seen that the adsorbent material loses its efficiency with subsequent recycle number. After recycling 4 times, the removal competence reduced to 47%. It was seen that the adsorbent worked with same capacity up to two runs and also, during third to fifth runs, it maintained a lower but almost a constant capacity. This can be elucidated as follows : when the adsorbent was desorbed first time certain chemical interaction must have taken place between adsorbent-adsorbate which didn't

Fig. 11. Removal percent of AO-10 by using regenerated adsorbent.

allow complete desorption of dye ions from the adsorbent surface as chemical adsorption is irreversible, with the subsequent cycle of desorption i.e. during third recycle, the sites which permit interaction of adsorbate-adsorbent chemically through exchange of electrons were no more left and only those sites remained vacant where physical interaction or physisorption would have been possible. Therefore from third cycle of regeneration process, physical adsorption becomes dominant and the removal efficiency of the AO-10 remains constant.

Experimental

Adsorbate : The anionic dye Acid Orange 10 (AO-10) also known as Orange G having chemical formula of $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Na}_2\text{O}_7\text{S}_2$ with FW of 452.37, was procured from Merck India (P.) Limited, Mumbai. The chemical structure of Acid Orange 10 is listed in Fig. 4. Orange G (C.I. No. 16230) having 99.0% of purity was used for the preparation dye solution without further purification. Stock solution of the test reagent was made by dissolving $2.21 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ of dye in 1 litre of double distilled water. The stock solution was further diluted with distilled water to obtain the standard solutions of 2.21×10^{-5} , 5.52×10^{-5} , 1.11×10^{-4} and $1.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

Adsorbent : All the reagents, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck, Mumbai), DTO (Hopkin & Williams, England), ethanol absolute (Changshu Yangyuan Chemical, China) and ammonium hydroxide (Merck, Mumbai) were of analytical grade and were used as such without any further puri-

fication. The complex of copper with dithiooxamide was prepared according to procedure reported by Abboudi and Mosset³³. Accurate amount of 0.5 g of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.3 g of dithiooxamide (DTO) were dissolved separately in 250 mL beaker containing 50 mL of ethanol, and the solutions were stirred for 2 h to form a homogeneous solution. The DTO solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution under stirring conditions subsequently followed by the addition of 25 mL of liquor ammonia. The resultant solution was again kept for stirring for another 2 h, which resulted in formation of black colored precipitate of Cu-DTO complex. The black precipitate was washed several times with distilled water and ethanol and eventually dried at 50 °C for 4 h.

Characterization of the prepared materials :

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the adsorbent material were recorded on a Rigaku/D-max 2000 diffractometer operated at 40 kV/20 mA, using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range of 5°–45°.

The presence of functional group in the sample was determined by FT-IR spectra analysis. The spectrum was recorded at room temperature on FTLA-2000 ABB, Canada, FTIR spectrophotometer in the range of 4000–500 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . Pellets were prepared with 13 mm KBr die set by compressing an intimate mixture obtained by grinding 1 mg of the substance in 100 mg of KBr with mortar and pestle and applying an optimum pressure of 9 ton using a 15 ton hydraulic pellet pressure (Kimaya Engineers, Thane).

Adsorption studies :

The batch experiments were conducted in order to optimize various operating parameters that affect the adsorption process of AO-10 by Cu-DTO as an adsorbent. To carry out batch adsorption studies, 100 mL dye solution of desired concentration was taken in a conical flask of 250 ml at a fixed temperature. The mixture was mechanically shaken at a constant speed of 180 rpm using water bath shaker (Mac-Macro Scientific Works, Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India). The samples were withdrawn after predetermined time, and kept it for 24 h for saturation. Thereafter, the adsorbent was separated from the solution by centrifugation using Remi centrifuge machine (Model-R-8CBL). The residual dye concentration was estimated in supernatant spectrophotometrically on double

beam spectrophotometer (Model-2203 Systronics, Ahmadedabad, India) over a wavelength of 480 nm. The effect of initial pH on the adsorption process was studied over a pH range of 2.0 to 10 being adjusted using 0.1 M NaOH or 0.1 M HCl. The adsorption isotherm experiments were carried out with dye solutions of different concentrations (2.21×10^{-5} to $1.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) and were stirred with the known amount of adsorbent (1 g/L) at different temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K) till the equilibrium was achieved. Adsorption kinetic investigation were carried out at different time intervals with four different initial dye concentrations keeping temperature, pH, adsorbent dose and shaking speed constant. The residual dye concentrations were analyzed from the calibration curve plotted between absorbance and concentration of dye solution.

The amount of dye adsorbed onto the adsorbent at equilibrium, q_e (mg/g), can be calculated by using relationship :

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_e) V/W \quad (7)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium dye concentration in mg/L respectively, V is the volume of solution (L) and W is the mass of adsorbent (g).

The removal percentage (%) of dye was calculated using the following equation :

$$\text{Dye removal \%} = (C_0 - C_e) \times 100/C_0 \quad (8)$$

Blank experiments were also conducted by using dye solution without adsorbent to ensure that no dye was adsorbed onto the containers and with adsorbent and water only to check that no leaching occurred from the prepared adsorbent, which would rather interfere with the measurement of dye concentrations on the spectrophotometer. All adsorption experiments were performed in triplicate and the mean values were taken for the data analysis.

Conclusion

In this work, the adsorption of Acid Orange 10 by metal-organic framework material (Cu-DTO complex) from aqueous phase was discussed. The factors that influenced the removal process were pH, initial concentration and temperature. The interaction between adsorbate-adsorbent being assessed by equilibrium isotherm study and the data support Freundlich isotherm model. The determination of reaction mechanism and rate controlling

steps were carried out by conducting kinetic experiments and the process of removal followed second order kinetics. Thermodynamics expression indicated the feasibility and exothermic nature of adsorption process. Therefore, on the basis of above discussion, Cu-DTO complex can be considered as promising candidate for the removal of dye from aqueous solutions.

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